

Liji 禮記

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Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Pre-Qin Confucian Traditions, Religious Group, Imperial Confucian Traditions, Chinese Religion, Text, Confucian Classics, Early Chinese text, Confucianism, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

The Liji 禮記, translated as "Record of Rites" or "Book of Rites", is a collection of essays on rituals and ritual principles written between the Warring States period (475-221 B.C.E.) to the Han Dynasty (202 B.C.E.-220). Scholars conventionally believed that this anthology belonged to the Confucian tradition and was recorded and compiled by Confucius's disciples. The received Liji has been said to be transmitted by Dai Sheng 戴聖 (fl. 1th century B.C.E.) in the Han and called Xiao Dai Liji 小戴禮記 alternatively to differ from the Da Dai Liji 大戴禮記 transmitted by Dai Sheng's uncle Dai De 戴德 (fl. 1th century B.C.E.). The Liji, the Yili 儀禮, and the Zhouli 周禮 were known together as Sanli 三禮. Nevertheless, the three Classics have different focuses. The received Liji has 49 chapters in total, and although they also touch upon various idealized rituals which were thought to be institutionalized in high antiquity, including sacrifice, wedding, capping, and funerary rituals, the Liji chapters concentrate on discussing the principles behind the ritual and social norms. For instance, the "Daxue" 大學 chapter detailed the steps through which one could successfully govern the world, while the "Liyun" 禮運 chapter illustrated how an ordered society could be achieved when propriety could be applied in reality. Zheng Xuan's 鄭玄 (127-200) commentary on the Liji, which we can now read from the Wujing Zhengyi 五經正義 recension in which Kong Yingda's 孔穎達 (574-648) sub-commentary were also included, is probably the earliest surviving and most authoritative commentary among others, even though revisions and criticisms of Zheng Xuan's commentary can still be found in our available materials. Recent archeological excavations have discovered numerous manuscripts which are counterparts and variants of the chapters being incorporated into the anthology under discussion. The textual parallels of certain Liji chapters suggest that the chapters (or even sections) of the Liji had been circulated separately and independently before they reached their current form. For instance, both the Guodian and Shanghai Museum collections of the Chu bamboo-slips contain counterparts of a chapter entitled "Zi Yi" 緇衣 in the Liji. The excavated versions of the "Zi Yi" are different from the transmitted one. Putting aside the difference in their wordings and lengths, scholars have recognized that a major difference is their sequences. That Liji chapters were first transmitted and circulated separately and that there was the difference in the textual sequence of certain received Liji chapters were also acknowledged by certain Daoxue 道學 (better known as Neo-Confucian) fellows, such as Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200) in the Song Dynasty. Arguing that the "Daxue" 大學 and "Zhongyong" 中庸 chapters of the Liji should be extracted from the anthology, Zhu Xi believed that both texts were as of equal importance to the Analects and the Mencius and that the four texts should be put together to form the Sishu 四書 (Four Books). Zhu Xi even rearranged the sequence of the "Daxue" and added a new sentence. Zhu Xi's recension of the "Daxue" and "Zhongyong" had become the standard version for imperial examinations since 13th century when Zhu Xi's teachings were accepted as state orthodoxy.

Date Range: 551 BCE - 1911 CE

Region: Pre-modern China

Region tags: China, East Asia, Shandong

Core area in which the Liji was circulated in pre-modern China

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kong Yingda 孔穎達 ed. Liji Zhengyi 禮記正義, Shisanjing zhushu 十三經注疏, Ruan Yuan 阮元 ed. Taipei: Yiwen yinshu guan yinhang, 2001.
- Source 2: Sun Xidan 孫希旦. Liji jijie 禮記集解. Beijing : Zhong hua shu ju, 1989.
- Source 3: Wang Mengou 王夢鷗. Liji jinzhu jinshi 禮記今註今釋. Taipei: Taiwan shangwu, 1980.

Reference: Riegel, Jeffrey K.. “Li Chi 禮記”. In *Early Chinese Texts: A Bibliographical Guide*, 293–97. Berkeley: Society for the Study of Early China, 1993.

Reference: Ing, Michael. *The Dysfunction of Ritual in Early Confucianism*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2012.

Reference: Ing, Michael. *The Vulnerability of Integrity in Early Confucian Thought*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2017.

Reference: Legge, James. *The Sacred Books of China: The Texts of Confucianism, Part 3-4, the Li Ki*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1885.

Reference: Lau 劉殿爵, D. C., and Fong Ching 方正 Chen 陳. Liji Zhuzi Suoyin 禮記逐字索引. Taipei: Taiwan shangwu yinshuguan, 1992.

Reference: Roger, Ames. “Observing Ritual ‘propriety (li 禮)’ as Focusing the ‘familiar’ in the Affairs of the Day”. *Dao: A Journal of Comparative Philosophy* 1, no. 2 (June 1, 2002).

Reference: Pines, Yuri. *Foundations of Confucian Thought: Intellectual Life in the Chunqiu Period, 722–453 B.C.E.* Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2002.

Reference: Fehl, Noah Edward. *Li: Rites and Propriety in Literature and Life—a Perspective for a Cultural History of Ancient China*. Hong Kong: Chinese University of Hong Kong, 1971.

Reference: Zhang 張, Yinshu 銀樹. Liji Sixiang Conglun 禮記思想叢論. Taipei: Furen Daxue Chubanshe, 2006.

Reference: Choi, Mihwa. *Death Rituals and Politics in Northern Song China*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2017.

Reference: Luo 羅, Jianwei 健蔚. Zheng Xuan Huitong San Li Yanjiu 鄭玄會通三《禮》研究. Taipei: Xin wenfeng chuban gufen youxian gongsi, 2020.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/liji>
- Source 1 Description: CText 中國哲學書電子化計劃
- Source 2 URL: <http://hanchi.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/ihp/hanji.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Scripta Sinica 漢籍電子文獻資料庫

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/>

– Source 1 Description: CText, corpus of the ancient Chinese texts

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Tool for making the impression(s)

– Other [specify]: Although texts were written and copied through handwriting before the 11th century when the printing technique was introduced, paper had already been the major medium for writing since at the latest the Tang Dynasty.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: Paper was the major written medium in imperial China since the Han. When print technology was introduced to China, the editions of Liji were majorly produced through woodblock printing.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Although texts were written and copied through handwriting before the 11th century when the printing technique was introduced, paper had already been the major medium for writing since at the latest the Tang Dynasty.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– **Bamboo**

Notes: In the pre-imperial and early imperial periods, texts were mainly written on bamboo (as well as silk). We see certain variants of the current Liji's chapters from newly discovered bamboo-slip manuscripts. For instance, the "Zi Yi" 緇衣 chapter has two variants from both the Guodian and Shanghai museum collections.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– **Silk**

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– **No**

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– **Physical preparation**

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– **No**

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– **Other [specify]:** Highly possible. Although we do not know the motivations for the modifications, the variants of certain chapters of the received Liji suggest that they were modified wither consciously or unconsciously.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Tool for making the impression(s)

- Other [specify]: Although texts were written and copied through handwriting before the 11th century when the printing technique was introduced, paper had already been the major medium for writing since at the latest the Tang Dynasty.

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Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

— I don't know

Notes: The issue is complicated. The Liji contains a couple of chapters which discuss the details of certain rituals (such as sacrifices and mourning) and the principles between the rituals, the anthology in and by itself is better not to be understood as a religious scripture given that whether the Confucianism, a tradition to which this anthology belongs, is a religion remains controversial. In the Han Dynasty, the dynasty in which Confucianism started to be the state orthodoxy of Chinese imperium, the current Liji was not part of the Five Classics. It was not until the Tang Dynasty when the Wujing zhengyi 五經正義 was compiled under the leadership of Kong Yingda 孔穎達 (574-648) did the current Liji become one of the Five Classics. However, the Liji as one of the Five Classics was not a "scripture" in the strictest sense. Rather, it was more an authoritative text for civil examination.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

— No

Notes: The variety of rituals that the Liji includes were performed for different purposes and took place in accordance with the seasons. However, some rituals maybe conducted in certain points of one's life. For instance, the ceremony of capping took place when the person who was capped grew up as an adult. The ritual of funeral took place after one's death. The sacrifices were supposed to show the respects of the participants (usually the offspring). In general, the rituals in the anthology were thought as means to maintain the social order.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The relationship of body and mind in the Liji is different from the western perspectives. In short, body and mind were thought to be intricate in the Liji

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: spirit(mind) and body were intricate but not separated nor in opposite positions.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The mind-body relationship in the Liji and other early Chinese texts was different from that in the West. While the western philosophers saw the mind and the body as separated, early Chinese thinkers believed that they were actually two sides of a coin. One's body was the embodiment of his inner morality and the medium through which rituals could cultivate one's mind.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: Scholars of the Confucian tradition in imperial China were inclined to believe that one's physical body is the embodiment of his morality.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The Liji included and regulated various rituals that were supposed to be performed for different purposes. The rituals include ancestral and spiritual sacrifices, funeral and mourning, capping ceremony, archery ceremony, and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Ritual manual

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Liji includes a series of vocabulary used for moral and ritual discourses. For instance, the "Zhongyong" 中庸, "Daxue" 大學, "Yue ji" 樂記 chapters and so on illuminates such philosophical terms as cheng 誠 (sincerity), xing 性 (nature), ming 命 (destiny), Datong 大同 (Great Union). These terms have been extensively studied and interpreted throughout the history.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Calligraphy?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Illustrations?

— Yes

Notes: Several illustrations of the artifacts recorded in the Liji as well as other two ritual Classics-- Yili 儀禮 and Zhouli 周禮--were produced in imperial China. In the Han Dynasty, Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 wrote the Sanlitu 三禮圖 to visualize the recorded ritual performances, gestures, and artifacts. Although Zheng Xuan's illustration had long been lost, its fragments, together with other illustrations, were included in Nie Chongyi's 聶崇義 Sanlitu, which was one of the most important illustration of the three ritual Classics in medieval China.

Reference: François, Louis. Design by the Book: Chinese Ritual Objects and the Sanli Tu. New York: Bard Graduate Center, 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Illuminations?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

— No

Notes: It has been said that the Liji was transmitted by Dai Sheng and was different from the Da Dai Liji 大戴禮記 transmitted by Dai De.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Monogamy (females)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: In the "Neize" 内則 chapter, it was prescribed that a male should have sex with his wife and concubines who were less than fifty-year-old once per five days

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: A wife was required to clean her body, wore formally, and have ornaments before having sex with her husband. A concubine must come after the legal wife and could not stay with her husband for a whole night.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

Notes: In the "Tan Gong II" chapter, we read of the story in which Chen Qianxi 陳乾昔 asked his son to bury his living slave girls after his death. Although his son refused to do so, this story implies that human sacrifice was a common practice in the pre-imperial period. The Liji, however, argued that there is a boundary between the dead and the living men and disagreed with the practice of human sacrifice. Confucius in the same chapter even criticized the creator of yong 俑 (wooden figures of living men), which were used in substitution for the living men, was buren 不仁 (not benevolent), for the use of yong was still close to human sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

— Yes

Notes: Metaphysics, particularly that in the "Daxue" and "Zhongyong" chapters, became an issue vividly debated in the Song Dynasty. Arguing that the world is dominated by the constant principle (li 理), Zhu Xi and other Daoxue fellows believed that the moral norms promoted in the Confucian Classics were the manifestations of the li 理. Human nature/ disposition (xing 性) was thought in the "Zhongyong" chapter as something mandated by Heaven, "What Heaven has conferred is called The Nature" 天命之謂性 (James Legge's translation). The xing was a fundamental metaphysical base for human's moral behaviors that, although xing was easily interfered by external factors, could be cultivated through education. Thus, the final purpose of education was thought to cultivate one's morality that all behaviors of human beings would not violate any moral norms Confucianism set forth.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: As demonstrated above, several chapters of the received Liji, such as the "Zi Yi" and "Kongzi Xian Ju", have their variants in recently discovered bamboo-slip manuscripts from the pre-imperial era.

Reference: Richter, Matthias L.. *The Embodied Text: Establishing Textual Identity in Early Chinese*

Manuscripts. Leiden: Brill, 2013.

Reference: Shaughnessy, Edward. *Rewriting Early Chinese Texts*. Albany: SUNY Press, 2006.

Reference: Kern, Martin. "Quotation and the Confucian Canon in Early Chinese Manuscripts: The Case of 'zi Yi' (black Robes)". *Asiatische Studien / Études Asiatiques* 59, no. 1 (April 1, 2005).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there debate about which version is proper?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

— I don't know

Notes: In the Song Dynasty, the "Da Xue" and "Zhongyong" chapters were taken out from the entire anthology and valued by the Daoxue fellows, particularly Zhu Xi, as the texts comparable to the Analects and the Mencius. Challenged the widely acknowledged version of the "Da Xue", Zhu Xi reordered the sequence of the "Da Xue" and added a new line to it. The revised "Da Xue" were celebrated by the scholar-officials in the early modern period for Zhu Xi and his teachings were privileged over others as the orthodox imperial philosophy.

Reference: Gardner, Daniel K.. *Chu Hsi and the Ta-hsueh: Neo-confucian Reflection on the Confucian Canon*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1986.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require castration?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text express a formal legal code?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Liji, as one of the Confucian classics, promoted a series of Confucian values, including ren 仁 (benevolence), yi 義 (righteousness), jing 敬 (sincerity), and so on. All of these values aimed to create a harmonious society in which social hierarchy be maintained.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

— Yes

Notes: Xiao 孝 appears multiple times throughout the entire anthology, which emphasizes the privilege of the seniors (parents, ancestors, and so on) of a family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cooperation

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moderation/frugality

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: In the Liji and other early Chinese texts, the attractiveness of one's physical body was relevant to one's inner morality. One's physical body was the embodiment of his morality. A gentleman was required to have demeanor (weiyi 威儀).

Reference: Lin 林, Su-Wen 素玟. "Jishen Hande, Yi Ti Jianli—Liji De Shenti Meixue' 即身涵德、以體踐禮—《禮記》的身體美學". *Chengda Zhongwen Xuebao 成大中文學報* 65 (June 1, 2019).

Reference: Csikszentmihalyi, Mark. *Material Virtue: Ethics and the Body in Early China*. Leiden: Brill, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The moral virtues listed above were supposed to set the foundation for the well-ordered world according to the "Daxue" 大學 chapter. Only when one perfects the above-mentioned virtues or cultivates himself (xiushen修身), can he manage his family. And only when he can successfully manage his family, can he govern a state. Only when he can successfully govern the state, can he pacify the world.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cremation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Mummification?

– No

Notes: Although the Liji does not prescribe any method of mummification similar to that in the ancient Egypt, the corpse of a dead will be cleaned carefully by the aides before slighter dressing (xiaolian 小斂, which means to put a dress on a dead).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Interment?**

— Yes

Notes: Interment was the most typical way to deal with the corpses in ancient China. Usually coffins were used to protect the corpses from being decomposed by bugs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Cannibalism?**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Feeding to animals?**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Secondary burial?**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Re-treatment of corpse?**

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ **Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Liji has long been seen as one of the Classics of the Confucian tradition. However, the Confucian tradition was officially established in the Han Dynasty. Thus, it would be an anachronism to ascribe the pre-imperial variants of the Liji's chapters to the Confucian tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" 月令 chapter, in particular, prescribes the dates for performing or inhibiting specific activities ((ritual, agricultural, musical, military, and so on) in a calendar year.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Planting?

– Yes

Notes: The son of Heaven was required to work in the field in the first month of the year to instruct the common people so that agricultural activities could be conducted without error: "They must thus instruct and lead on the people, themselves also engaging in the tasks. The business of the fields being thus ordered, the guiding line is first put in requisition, and the husbandry is carried on without error" 五穀所殖，以教道民，必躬親之。田事既飭，先定準直，農乃不惑 (James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Harvest?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Marriage?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divorce?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Warfare?

— Yes

Notes: Military activity was not allowed in the first month of a year, according to the "Yueling" chapter: "In this month no warlike operations should be undertaken; the undertaking of such is sure to be followed by calamities from Heaven" 是月也，不可以稱兵，稱兵必天殃 (James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: Each festival, in principle, was celebrated once per year.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: I do know. The number varies depending on the size of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Pilgramages?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specify

– Specify: ancestral temple, palace, and so on, depending on the types of feast.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice was harshly criticized in the Confucian tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Vigil and fasting were required on or before certain ceremonies, such as sacrifices. According to the "Yueling" 月令 chapter, different members of the society were also required to practice vigil and fasting in certain months respectively.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Personal effects?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

Notes: The "Tan Gong" 檀弓 chapter records that mingqi 明器 (James Legge's translation: vessels only to the eye of fancy) were placed in graves at burials. However, the materials used to make mingqi were valueless. They were significant for they symbolized the spiritual status of the dead. However, bearing a significant value did not mean the grave goods are all luxurious. The recent archeological findings from pre-imperial and early imperial tombs demonstrate a situation different from that in the Liji. Luxurious goods and objects have been excavated frequently from the ancient tombs, questioning the acceptance of the Liji restriction.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– No

Notes: The mingqi were not supposed to be either useful or practical. In the "Tan Gong II" chapter, Confucius argued that if the mingqi were useful, it was no more than the interment of living men.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: As recorded in the "Tan Gong I" chapter, the case of duke Xiang of Song, who placed a hundred of jars which were full of vinegar and pickles in his wife's grave, demonstrated that objects other than the mingqi were commonly put in the graves in the pre-imperial era.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: The "Tang Gong I" chapter recorded a speech by Confucius, in which Confucius said that graves usually did not have mound over them in antiquity. However, the reason for Confucius to raise a mound over the grave of his parents was that he was about to wander the world and the mound served as a signal for him to remember where were his parents buried.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: In the "Bensang" 奔喪 chapter, the Liji discussed the different ways of hurrying to attend the mourning and funeral rituals in accordance with one's relation with the dead. The closer their relationship is, the hastier one should go. The chapter also prescribed the complicated procedures for the funerary ritual for different attendants and regulate the practices if attending the funerary ritual was impossible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: In the "Tan Gong II" and "Wensong" chapters, it was said that women would piyong 辟踊 (beat their breast) in funerary rituals as a way to express their sorrow or grief.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: The descendants of the dead must mourn the dead in the following three years. In this duration, they were requested to live in an unadorned and assiduous way. For instance, in the "San Nian Wen" 三年間 chapter, it was said that they should wear plain mourning clothes and eat porridge, which were used to express their sorrow.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

For the worship of a deified human?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: The three-year mourning was said in the Analects to one's veneration of their parents. According to the Analects, since everyone was protected in the arms of their parents in the first three years of their life, they should spend three years equally to show their respect and gratitude for their parents. In the Liji, Confucius further reminded others that their sorrow should be expressed appropriately and excessive sorrow was not recommended.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Normally called Shangdi 上帝 or Tian 天. It is believed among certain scholars, such as Chang Chung-ying and D. Keightley, that in the early age of the Shang Dynasty, Shangdi was the ancestor of the Shang royal house. However, Shangdi became a deity who was not the ancestor of the royal house anymore. Chen Mengjia, in contrast, argued that the Shang ancestor and the Shangdi were two different deities that one should not mix them up. No matter what, in Zhou discourse, Shangdi became a supreme deity who was completely from the ancestors of the Zhou royal house. According to the Shijing, the ancestors of the Zhou ruling house would stand by the Shangdi's side, implying that they were two different types of deities, with the Shangdi being the supreme one.

Reference: Chang, Chung-ying. *Early Chinese Civilization*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press,

1976.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

— Yes

Reference: Chang, Chung-ying. *Early Chinese Civilization*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1976.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

— No

Notes: The ruler was the Son of Heaven, not the Heaven per se.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

— No

Notes: The ruler was known as the Son of Heaven, which represented a fictive kinship between the ruler and the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

— Yes

Notes: The rulers were called the Son of Heaven (tianzi 天子) in the Liji, implying that the ruler of human world was a son of Heaven, the supreme god in Chinese thought. It should be noted that the title of Son of Heaven was used by rulers to authorize their divine right to govern but could not verify the biological relation between the supreme god and rulers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: The tian has the absolute right to decide who is qualified as the ruler of the mortal world and bestows the right of governing upon a suitable person (with accumulated de 德)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god/ tian in the Liji and other early Chinese texts basically knows everything in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Possesses Hunger?

— I don't know

Notes: The Liji mentioned the qi and fragrance of the foods offered to the deities. The more fragrant the foods were, the higher the deity they could reach. We do not know was it because the supreme high god felt hungry that he received the food sacrifices.

Reference: Sterckx, Roel. *Food, Sacrifice, and Sagehood in Early China*. Cambridge University Press, 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be hurt?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be tricked?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be imprisoned?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

— Specify: Heaven could hear the complaints by common people and decide whether a royal house was qualified to possess the heavenly mandate.

Notes: The mandate of Heaven was a political concept developed in the Zhou dynasty. To be eligible for possessing the mandate of Heaven, a royal house was requested to accumulate enough virtuous power (de 德) by its dynastic rulers. The depletion of de would result in the loss of heavenly mandate, and the mandate of Heaven would then shift to another family which had already accumulated enough virtuous power. Thus, a ruler was requested to fulfil his moral duties as a ruler and keep a vigilant eye on his

immortal behaviors that might lead to the loss of his de.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In dreams

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The human spirits in the Liji were called guishen 鬼神 (ghosts and gods). It was said that human beings would transform into guishen after death. In general, human spirit consisted of two complementary components: hun 魂 and po 魄. The former will ascend to Heaven while the latter will dive into Earth after the death of a human being. The concept that human spirit consisted of hun and po was closely related to the concept of yin and yang in which both components interact with each other and were complementary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

Notes: In the "Biao Ji" 表記 chapter, it was said that the ghosts and gods would not impose harm on the royal house if sacrifices and the ceremonies were perfectly prepared and performed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: It is believed in the Confucian tradition that one's body was given by his/ her parents that one was not allowed to harm his/her physical body, not to mention suicide.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Although Confucius himself did not want to talk about spirits in the world, it was the Confucian concept spirits did exist in the world. Gui 鬼 were transformed from human beings when the latter died, while shen 神 referred to the deities living in the natural world. Although the spirits should be respected, it was argued that human should keep a distance with the spirits, and human beings' respect to the spirits and the sacrifices they offered to the spirits were aimed to serve the mundane world. The following passage from the "Biao ji" 表記 chapter demonstrated how Confucius discussed the issue of spirits: Under the Xia dynasty it was the way to give honour to the nature conferred on men; they served the manes of the departed, and respected Spiritual Beings, keeping them at a distance, while they brought the people near, and made them loyal; they put first the (attraction) of emolument, and last the terrors of power; first rewards, and then punishments; showing their affection (for the people), but not giving them honour. The bad effect on the people was, that they became stupid and ignorant, proud and clownish, and uncultivated, without any accomplishments. Under the Yin dynasty, they honoured Spiritual Beings, and led the people on to serve them; they put first the service of their manes, and last the usages of ceremony; first punishments, and then rewards; giving honour (to the people), but not showing affection for them. The bad effect on the people was, that they became turbulent and were restless, striving to surpass one another without any sense of shame. Under the Zhou dynasty, they honoured the ceremonial usages, and set a high value on bestowing (favours); they served the manes and respected Spiritual Beings, yet keeping them at a distance; they brought the people near, and made them loyal; in rewarding and punishing they used the various distinctions and arrangements of rank; showing affection (for the people), but not giving them honour. The bad effects on the people were, that they became fond of gain and crafty; were all for accomplishments, and shameless; injured one another, and had their moral sense obscured. 夏道尊命，事鬼敬神而遠之，近人而忠焉，先祿而後威，先賞而後罰，親而不尊；其民之敝：蠢而愚，喬而野，樸而不文。殷人尊神，率民以事神，先鬼而後禮，先罰而後賞，尊而不親；其民之敝：蕩而不靜，勝而無恥。周人尊禮尚施，事鬼敬神而遠之，近人而忠焉，其賞罰用爵列，親而不尊；其民之敝：利而巧，文而不慚，賊而蔽。(James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: The "Zhongyong" 中庸 chapter said that what will happen in the future will be shown on shigui 蓍龜 (milfoil and tortoise) divination, implying that the non-human spirits were prophetic.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge of the cosmic operations (yinyang 陰陽).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

Notes: Same as the supreme high god (shangdi), they received sacrificial foods from human beings. However, we do not know did they possess hunger.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: In the "Yue Ling" 月令, we read of four deities who represented a specific season in a year respectively. They are Guomang 句芒 (Spring), Zhurong 祝融 (Summer), Rushou 蓐收 (Autumn), and Xuanming 玄冥 (Winter).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: The pyromantic divination results (in the form of crack) were usually shown on tortoise shell.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Divination through human communication?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: Bones, Flame, and milfoil

Notes: The divinatory cracks were made after the animal bones (tortoise shell) were burned. Milfoil sticks were also used for divination.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other form of divination:

– Specify: Oneiromancy

Notes: In the "Tan Gong I" chapter, Confucius provided an example of divination based upon dream. Dreaming that he was sitting together with the offerings to the dead in the middle of two pillars, Confucius predicted his approaching death.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: Number of participants depended on the scale of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals recorded in the Liji were differently interpreted by certain classicists such as Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 (127-200). Their interpretations were accepted in different points of history as state orthodoxies. However, by no means we should see their interpretations as the correct understanding of the recorded ritual practices because they were treated as orthodoxies.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

Notes: The word "Son of Heaven" tianzi 天子 was a fictive kinship terminology applied only to the rulers who had received heavenly mandate before ascending to the throne.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Drama?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Comedy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Tragedy?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Epic entertainment?

— Yes

Notes: Musical performances and dancing were typical entertainments recorded in the Liji, and they were performed in every ceremony. Usually, the odes recorded in the "Hymns" and "Eulogies" sections of the Shijing 詩經 would be sung accompanied with dancing. For the performativity of the odes in the Shijing, see, for instance: Kern, Martin. 2000. "Shi jing Songs as Performance Texts: A Case Study of 'Chu ci' ('Thorny Caltrop')." *Early China* (25): 49-111. _____. 2009. "Bronze inscriptions, the Shangshu, and the Shijing: The Evolution of the Ancestral Sacrifice during the Western Zhou." In John Lagerwey and Marc Kalinowski ed. *Early Chinese Religion, Part One: Shang Through Han (1250 BC to 220 AD)*. Leiden: Brill, 143-200.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

— Yes

Notes: There were several sacred spaces mentioned in the Liji. In these sacred spaces, different types of sacrifice were held for different purposes. The mingtang 明堂 was an architecture within which sacrifices were held. It was said that the sacrifices held in the mingtang could teach people the importance of filial piety and the distinction between superiority and inferiority. The seasonal offerings were held, according to the "Qu li xia" 曲禮下, in the wusi 五祀 (hu 戶, zao 竈, zhongliu 中霤, men 門, hang 行). In addition, people were prescribed to offer sacrifices to Heaven and Earth in taitan 泰壇 and taishe 泰折 respectively.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Animal sacrifice?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Human sacrifice, although was a common practice in early China, was not recommended by the Liji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: Meat was used as food sacrifices in the Liji. In ancient China, meat was one of the valuable ingredients.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: As above mentioned, the smells of the foods were supposed to deliver to the deities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: In the "Mingtang Wei" 明堂位 chapter, it was said that the Three Dynasties (i.e., the Xia, Shang, and Zhou) had different preferences for the colors of the sacrifices: "The sovereigns of Xia preferred black victims; those of Yin, white; and those of Zhou, victims which were red and strong" 夏后氏，牲尚黑，殷白牡，周騂剛. (translated by James Legge)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other?

– Specify: no

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ By the community?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The text regulated how many temples members of a society could have in accordance with their rankings. However, it did not talk about the maintenance of the temples, in which ceremonies took place.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: Several illustrations of the artifacts recorded in the Liji as well as other two ritual Classics--Yili 儀禮 and Zhouli 周禮--were produced in imperial China. In the Han Dynasty, Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 wrote the Sanlitu 三禮圖 to visualize the recorded ritual performances, gestures, and artifacts. Although Zheng Xuan's illustration had long been lost, its fragments, together with other illustrations, were included in Nie Chongyi's 聶崇義 Sanlitu, which was one of the most important illustration of the three ritual Classics in medieval China.

Reference: François, Louis. Design by the Book: Chinese Ritual Objects and the Sanli Tu. New York: Bard Graduate Center, 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: As demonstrated above, several chapters of the received Liji, such as the "Zi Yi" and "Kongzi Xian Ju", have their variants in recently discovered bamboo-slip manuscripts from the pre-imperial era.

Reference: Richter, Matthias L. *The Embodied Text: Establishing Textual Identity in Early Chinese Manuscripts*. Leiden: Brill, 2013.

Reference: Shaughnessy, Edward. *Rewriting Early Chinese Texts*. Albany: SUNY Press, 2006.

Reference: Kern, Martin. "Quotation and the Confucian Canon in Early Chinese Manuscripts: The Case of 'Zi Yi' (black Robes)." *Asiatische Studien / Études Asiatiques* 59, no. 1 (April 1, 2005).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– I don't know

Notes: In the Song Dynasty, the "Da Xue" and "Zhongyong" chapters were taken out from the entire anthology and valued by the Daoxue fellows, particularly Zhu Xi, as the texts comparable to the Analects and the Mencius. Challenged the widely acknowledged version of the "Dao Xue", Zhu Xi reordered the sequence of the "Da Xue" and added a new line to it. The revised "Da Xue" were celebrated by the scholar-officials in the early modern period for Zhu Xi and his teachings were privileged over others as the orthodox imperial philosophy.

Reference: Gardner, Daniel K. *Chu Hsi and the Ta-hsueh: Neo-confucian Reflection on the Confucian Canon*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1986.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Liji has long been seen as one of the Classics of the Confucian tradition. However, the Confucian tradition was officially established in the Han Dynasty. Thus, it would be an anachronism to ascribe the pre-imperial variants of the Liji's chapters to the Confucian tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The Liji included and regulated various rituals that were supposed to be performed for different purposes. The rituals include ancestral and spiritual sacrifices, funeral and mourning, capping ceremony, archery ceremony, and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Ritual manual

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Liji includes a series of vocabulary used for moral and ritual discourses. For instance, the "Zhongyong" 中庸, "Daxue" 大學, "Yue ji" 樂記 chapters and so on illuminates such philosophical terms as

cheng 誠 (sincerity), xing 性 (nature), ming 命 (destiny), Datong 大同 (Great Union). These terms have been extensively studied and interpreted throughout the history.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: It has been said that the Liji was transmitted by Dai Sheng and was different from the Da Dai Liji 大戴禮記 transmitted by Dai De.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" 月令 chapter, in particular, prescribes the dates for performing or inhibiting specific activities ((ritual, agricultural, musical, military, and so on) in a calendar year.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Planting?

– Yes

Notes: The son of Heaven was required to work in the field in the first month of the year to instruct the common people so that agricultural activities could be conducted

without error: "They must thus instruct and lead on the people, themselves also engaging in the tasks. The business of the fields being thus ordered, the guiding line is first put in requisition, and the husbandry is carried on without error" 五穀所殖，以教道民，必躬親之。田事既飭，先定準直，農乃不惑 (James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divorce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Military activity was not allowed in the first month of a year, according to the "Yueling" chapter: "In this month no warlike operations should be undertaken; the undertaking of such is sure to be followed by calamities from Heaven" 是月也，不可以稱兵，稱兵必天殃 (James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: Each festival, in principle, was celebrated once per year.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: I do know. The number varies depending on the size of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Pilgrimages?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specify

– Specify: ancestral temple, palace, and so on, depending on the types of feast.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The relationship of body and mind in the Liji is different from the western perspectives. In short, body and mind were thought to be intricate in the Liji

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: spirit(mind) and body were intricate but not separated nor in opposite positions.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The mind-body relationship in the Liji and other early Chinese texts was different from that in the West. While the western philosophers saw the mind and the body as separated, early Chinese thinkers believed that they were actually two sides of a coin. One's body was the embodiment of his inner morality and the medium through which rituals could cultivate one's mind.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: Scholars of the Confucian tradition in imperial China were inclined to believe that one's physical body is the embodiment of his morality.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cremation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Mummification?

– No

Notes: Although the Liji does not prescribe any method of mummification similar to that in the ancient Egypt, the corpse of a dead will be cleaned carefully by the aides before slighter dressing (xiaolian 小斂, which means to put a dress on a dead).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: Interment was the most typical way to deal with the corpses in ancient China. Usually coffins were used to protect the corpses from being decomposed by bugs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice was harshly criticized in the Confucian tradition.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Personal effects?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

Notes: The "Tan Gong" 檀弓 chapter records that mingqi 明器 (James Legge's translation: vessels only to the eye of fancy) were placed in graves at burials. However, the materials used to make mingqi were valueless. They were significant for they symbolized the spiritual status of the dead. However, bearing a significant value did not mean the grave goods are all luxurious. The recent archeological findings from pre-imperial and early imperial tombs demonstrate a situation different from that in the Liji. Luxurious goods and objects have been excavated frequently from the ancient tombs, questioning the acceptance of the Liji restriction.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– No

Notes: The mingqi were not supposed to be either useful or practical. In the "Tan Gong II" chapter, Confucius argued that if the mingqi were useful, it was no more than the interment of living men.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: As recorded in the "Tan Gong I" chapter, the case of duke Xiang of Song, who placed a hundred of jars which were full of vinegar and pickles in his wife's grave, demonstrated that objects other than the mingqi were commonly put in the graves in the pre-imperial era.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: The "Tang Gong I" chapter recorded a speech by Confucius, in which Confucius said that graves usually did not have mound over them in antiquity. However, the reason for Confucius to raise a mound over the grave of his parents was that he was about to wander the world and the mound served as a signal for him to remember where were his parents buried.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: In the "Bensang" 奔喪 chapter, the Liji discussed the different ways of hurrying to attend the mourning and funeral rituals in accordance with one's relation with the dead. The closer their relationship is, the hastier one should go. The chapter also prescribed the complicated procedures for the funerary ritual for different attendants and regulate the practices if attending the funerary ritual was impossible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: The descendants of the dead must mourn the dead in the following three years. In this duration, they were requested to live in an unadorned and assiduous way. For instance, in the "San Nian Wen" 三年問 chapter, it was said that they should wear plain mourning clothes and eat porridge, which were used to express their sorrow.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: The three-year mourning was said in the Analects to one's veneration of their parents. According to the Analects, since everyone was protected in the arms of their parents in the first three years of their life, they should spend three years equally to show their respect and gratitude for their parents. In the Liji, Confucius further reminded others that their sorrow should be expressed appropriately and excessive sorrow was not recommended.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Normally called Shangdi 上帝 or Tian 天. It is believed among certain scholars, such as Chang Chung-ying and D. Keightley, that in the early age of the Shang Dynasty, Shangdi was the ancestor of the Shang royal house. However, Shangdi became a deity who was not the ancestor of the royal house anymore. Chen Mengjia, in contrast, argued that the Shang ancestor and the Shangdi were two different deities that one should not mix them up. No matter what, in Zhou discourse, Shangdi became a supreme deity who was completely from the ancestors of the Zhou royal house. According to the Shijing, the ancestors of the Zhou

ruling house would stand by the Shangdi's side, implying that they were two different types of deities, with the Shangdi being the supreme one.

Reference: Chang, Chung-ying. *Early Chinese Civilization*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1976.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Reference: Chang, Chung-ying. *Early Chinese Civilization*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1976.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The ruler was the Son of Heaven, not the Heaven per se.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The ruler was known as the Son of Heaven, which represented a fictive kinship between the ruler and the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

Notes: The rulers were called the Son of Heaven (tianzi 天子) in the Liji, implying that the ruler of human world was a son of Heaven, the supreme god in Chinese thought. It should be noted that the title of Son of Heaven was used by rulers to authorize their divine right to govern but could not verify the biological relation between the supreme god and rulers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The tian has the absolute right to decide who is qualified as the ruler of the mortal world and bestows the right of governing upon a suitable person (with accumulated de 德)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god/ tian in the Liji and other early Chinese texts basically knows everything in the world.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– I don't know

Notes: The Liji mentioned the qi and fragrance of the foods offered to the deities. The more fragrant the foods were, the higher the deity they could reach. We do not know was it because the supreme high god felt hungry that he received the food sacrifices.

Reference: Sterckx, Roel. *Food, Sacrifice, and Sagehood in Early China*. Cambridge University Press, 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Heaven could hear the complaints by common people and decide whether a royal house was qualified to possess the heavenly mandate.

Notes: The mandate of Heaven was a political concept developed in the Zhou dynasty. To be eligible for possessing the mandate of Heaven, a royal house was requested to accumulate enough virtuous power (de 德) by its dynastic rulers. The depletion of de would result in the loss of heavenly mandate, and the mandate of Heaven would then shift to another family which had already accumulated enough virtuous power. Thus, a ruler was requested to fulfil his moral duties as a ruler and keep a vigilant eye on his immortal behaviors that might lead to the loss of his de.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In dreams

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The human spirits in the Liji were called guishen 鬼神 (ghosts and gods). It was said that human beings would transform into guishen after death. In general, human spirit consisted of two complementary components: hun 魂 and po 魄. The former will ascend to Heaven while the latter will dive into Earth after the death of a human being. The concept that human spirit consisted of hun and po was closely related to the concept of yin and yang in which both components interact with each other and were complementary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

Notes: In the "Biao Ji" 表記 chapter, it was said that the ghosts and gods would not impose harm on the royal house if sacrifices and the ceremonies were perfectly prepared and performed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Although Confucius himself did not want to talk about spirits in the world, it was the Confucian concept spirits did exist in the world. Gui 鬼 were transformed from human beings when the latter died, while shen 神 referred to the deities living in the natural world. Although the spirits should be respected, it was argued that human should keep a distance with the spirits, and human beings' respect to the spirits and the sacrifices they offered to the spirits were aimed to serve the mundane world. The following passage from the "Biao ji" 表記 chapter demonstrated how Confucius discussed the issue of spirits: Under the Xia dynasty it was the way to give honour to the nature conferred on men; they served the manes of the departed, and respected Spiritual Beings, keeping them at a distance, while they brought the people near, and made them loyal; they put first the (attraction) of emolument, and last the terrors of power; first rewards, and then punishments; showing their affection (for the people), but not giving them honour. The bad effect on the people was, that they became stupid and ignorant, proud and clownish, and uncultivated, without any accomplishments. Under the Yin dynasty, they honoured Spiritual Beings, and led the people on to serve them; they put first the service of their manes, and last the usages of ceremony; first punishments, and then rewards; giving honour (to the people), but not showing affection for them. The bad effect on the people was, that they became turbulent and were restless, striving to surpass one another without any sense of shame. Under the Zhou dynasty, they honoured the ceremonial usages, and set a high value on bestowing (favours); they served the manes and respected Spiritual Beings, yet keeping them at a distance; they brought the people near, and made them loyal; in rewarding and punishing they used the various distinctions and arrangements of rank; showing affection (for the people), but not giving them honour. The bad effects on the people were, that they became fond of gain and crafty; were all for accomplishments, and shameless; injured one another, and had their moral sense obscured. 夏道尊命，事鬼敬神而遠之，近人而忠焉，先祿而後威，先賞而後罰，親而不尊；其民之敝：蠢而愚，喬而野，樸而不文。殷人尊神，率民以事神，先鬼而後禮，先罰而後賞，尊而不親；其民之敝：蕩而不靜，勝而無恥。周人尊禮尚施，事鬼敬神而遠之，近人而忠焉，其賞罰用爵列，親而不尊；其民之敝：利而巧，文而不慚，賊而蔽。(James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: The "Zhongyong" 中庸 chapter said that what will happen in the future will be shown on shigui 蓍龜 (milfoil and tortoise) divination, implying that the non-human spirits were prophetic.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge of the cosmic operations (yinyang 陰陽).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

Notes: Same as the supreme high god (shangdi), they received sacrificial foods from human beings. However, we do not know did they possess hunger.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: In the "Yue Ling" 月令, we read of four deities who represented a specific season in a year respectively. They are Guomang 句芒 (Spring), Zhurong 祝融 (Summer), Rushou 蓐收

(Autumn), and Xuanming 玄冥 (Winter).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: The pyromantic divination results (in the form of crack) were usually shown on tortoise shell.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Divination through human communication?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: Bones, Flame, and milfoil

Notes: The divinatory cracks were made after the animal bones (tortoise shell) were burned. Milfoil sticks were also used for divination.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other form of divination:

– Specify: Oneiromancy

Notes: In the "Tan Gong I" chapter, Confucius provided an example of divination based upon dream. Dreaming that he was sitting together with the offerings to the dead in the middle of two pillars, Confucius predicted his approaching death.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

Notes: In the "Tan Gong II" chapter, we read of the story in which Chen Qianxi 陳乾昔 asked his son to to bury his living slave girls after his death. Although his son refused to do so, this story implies that human sacrifice was a common practice in the pre-imperial period. The Liji, however, argued that there is a boundary between the dead and the living men and disagreed with the practice of human sacrifice. Confucius in the same chapter even criticized the creator of yong 俑 (wooden figures of living men), which were used in substitution for the living men, was buren 不仁 (not benevolent), for the use of yong was still close to human sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: Metaphysics, particularly that in the "Daxue" and "Zhongyong" chapters, became an issue vividly debated in the Song Dynasty. Arguing that the world is dominated by the constant principle (li 理), Zhu Xi and other Daoxue fellows believed that the moral norms promoted in the Confucian Classics were the manifestations of the li 理. Human nature/ disposition (xing 性) was thought in the "Zhongyong" chapter as something mandated by Heaven, "What Heaven has conferred is called The Nature" 天命之謂性 (James Legge's translation). The xing was a fundamental metaphysical base for human's moral behaviors that, although xing was easily interfered by external factors, could be cultivated through education. Thus, the final purpose of education was thought to cultivate one's morality that all behaviors of human beings would not violate any moral norms Confucianism set forth.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of

anthropomorphic being

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Liji, as one of the Confucian classics, promoted a series of Confucian values, including ren 仁 (benevolence), yi 義 (righteousness), jing 敬 (sincerity), and so on. All of these values aimed to create a harmonious society in which social hierarchy be maintained.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Xiao 孝 appears multiple times throughout the entire anthology, which emphasizes the privilege of the seniors (parents, ancestors, and so on) of a family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: In the Liji and other early Chinese texts, the attractiveness of one's physical body was relevant to one's inner morality. One's physical body was the embodiment of his morality. A gentleman was required to have demeanor (weiyi 威儀).

Reference: Lin 林, Su-Wen 素玟. "Jishen Hande, Yi Ti Jianli—Liji De Shenti Meixue' 即身涵德、以體踐禮 — 《禮記》的身體美學". Chengda Zhongwen Xuebao 成大中文學報 65 (June 1, 2019).

Reference: Csikszentmihalyi, Mark. *Material Virtue: Ethics and the Body in Early China*. Leiden: Brill, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: The moral virtues listed above were supposed to set the foundation for the well-ordered world according to the "Daxue" 大學 chapter. Only when one perfects the above-mentioned virtues or cultivates himself (xiushen 修身), can he manage his family. And only when he can successfully manage his family, can he govern a state. Only when he can successfully govern the state, can he pacify the world.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Monogamy (males)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Monogamy (females)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: In the "Neize" 內則 chapter, it was prescribed that a male should have sex with his wife and concubines who were less than fifty-year-old once per five days

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: A wife was required to clean her body, wore formally, and have ornaments before having sex with her husband. A concubine must come after the legal wife and could not stay with her husband for a whole night.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Vigil and fasting were required on or before certain ceremonies, such as sacrifices. According to the "Yueling" 月令 chapter, different members of the society were also required to practice vigil and fasting in certain months respectively.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: In the "Tan Gong II" and "Wensong" chapters, it was said that women would piyong 辟踊 (beat their breast) in funerary rituals as a way to express their sorrow or grief.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: It is believed in the Confucian tradition that one's body was given by his/ her parents that one was not allowed to harm his/her physical body, not to mention suicide.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: Number of participants depended on the scale of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals recorded in the Liji were differently interpreted by certain classicists such as Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 (127-200). Their interpretations were accepted in different points of history as state orthodoxies. However, by no means we should see their interpretations as the correct understanding of the recorded ritual practices because they were treated as orthodoxies.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

Notes: The word "Son of Heaven" tianzi 天子 was a fictive kinship terminology applied only to the rulers who had received heavenly mandate before ascending to the throne.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Drama?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Comedy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Tragedy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Notes: Musical performances and dancing were typical entertainments recorded in the Liji, and they were performed in every ceremony. Usually, the odes recorded in the "Hymns" and "Eulogies" sections of the Shijing 詩經 would be sung accompanied with dancing. For the performativity of the odes in the Shijing, see, for instance: Kern, Martin. 2000. "Shi jing Songs as Performance Texts: A Case Study of 'Chu ci' ('Thorny Caltrop')." *Early China* (25): 49-111. _____. 2009. "Bronze inscriptions, the Shangshu, and the Shijing: The Evolution of the Ancestral Sacrifice during the Western Zhou." In John Lagerwey and Marc Kalinowski ed. *Early Chinese Religion, Part One: Shang Through Han (1250 BC to 220 AD)*. Leiden: Brill, 143-200.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: There were several sacred spaces mentioned in the Liji. In these sacred spaces, different types of sacrifice were held for different purposes. The mingtang 明堂 was an architecture within which sacrifices were held. It was said that the sacrifices held in the mingtang could teach people the importance of filial piety and the distinction between superiority and inferiority. The seasonal offerings were held, according to the "Qu li xia" 曲禮下, in the wusi 五祀 (hu 戶, zao 竈, zhongliu 中霤, men 門, hang 行). In addition, people were prescribed to offer sacrifices to Heaven and Earth in taitan 泰壇 and taise 泰折 respectively.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Human sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Human sacrifice, although was a common practice in early China, was not recommended by the Liji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: Meat was used as food sacrifices in the Liji. In ancient China, meat was one of the valuable ingredients.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: As above mentioned, the smells of the foods were supposed to deliver to the deities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: In the "Mingtang Wei" 明堂位 chapter, it was said that the Three Dynasties (i.e., the Xia, Shang, and Zhou) had different preferences for the colors of the sacrifices: "The sovereigns of Xia preferred black victims; those of Yin, white; and those of Zhou, victims which were red and strong" 夏后氏，牲尚黑，殷白牡，周騂剛. (translated by James Legge)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Other?

– Specify: no

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ By the community?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The text regulated how many temples members of a society could have in accordance with their rankings. However, it did not talk about the maintenance of the temples, in which ceremonies took place.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

— Yes

Notes: The "Wangzhi" chapter of the Liji presented a detailed and structural bureaucratic system that was supposed to be practiced in the ancient times. The system regulated the duties, lands, salaries, and so on, of the rulers and other officials in accordance with their rankings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

— Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" chapter regulated what officials were allowed or not allowed to do in different seasons or months.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Notes: The "Wangzhi" chapter mentioned the existence of public fields (gongtian 公田) in the ideal antiquity. Farmers were required to farm on the public fields. However, no tax was imposed on the public fields.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The institutionalized troops could only be sent to conquer and punish the unrighteous, accordingly to the "Yueling" chapter's description, "The son of Heaven also orders the leaders and commanders to choose men and sharpen weapons, to select and exercise those of distinguished merit, and to give their entire trust only to men whose services have been proved - thereby to correct all unrighteousness. (He instructs them also) to make enquiries about and punish the oppressive and insolent - thereby making it clear whom he loves and whom he hates, and giving effect to (the wishes of) the people, even the most distant from court" 天子乃命將帥，選士厲兵，簡練桀俊，專任有功，以征不義。詰誅暴慢，以明好惡，順彼遠方。 (James Legge's translation) Moreover, the troops were strictly trained and managed according to rituals. In the "Qu li shang" 曲禮上, it was said that "The majesty and dignity cannot be shown in assigning the different places at court, in the government of the armies, and in discharging the duties of office so as to secure the operation of the laws" 班朝治軍，蒞官行法，非禮威嚴不行 (James Legge's translation, slightly modified)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" chapter regulated the months of a year (e.g., the first month of spring 孟春之月) in which warfare was not allowed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: We cannot determine who were the producers of the chapters in the Liji. However, given that the Liji described in detail the ritual process and institution of government, it is reasonable to assume that the scholar-officials in the past participated in the production of the text. In the meantime, the emperors also had the right to decide the orthodox versions of the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Fishing

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Fishing

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Liji was one of the Confucian Classics since the Tang Dynasty and it was widely studied by Chinese literati (shi 士) in imperial China for the imperial examinations. The text was taught in local schools run by famous scholar-officials. For instance, it was one of the required readings in Bailudong Shuyuan 白鹿洞書院 when Zhu Xi was in charge of the academy. In addition, the Liji was also one of the Classics studied by imperial rulers (such an institutions had been called Jingyan 經筵 since the Song Dynasty).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yue Ling" 月令 chapter discusses how the misuse of seasonal proceedings would lead to famine. It therefore urges that governmental proceedings should be put into practice in accordance with the proper seasons to avoid such a disaster.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: It is said in the "Yue Ling" 月令 chapter that in the last month of the Spring, the ruler would open his granaries and distributed his foods to impoverished people. The ruler would also open his treasuries and share the silks and other articles to people in the world: "是月也，生氣方盛，陽氣發泄，句者畢出，萌者盡達。不可以內。天子布德行惠，命有司發倉廩，賜貧窮，振乏絕，開府庫，出幣帛，周天下。勉諸侯，聘名士，禮賢者。"

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Literati or scholar-officials; emperors

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The elites in the Liji were supposed to start learning when they were young. The "Xueji" 學記 chapter demonstrated the system of ancient teaching, the names of school on different level, and what were supposed to learn at different stages: According to the system of ancient teaching, for the families of (a hamlet) there was the village school; for a neighbourhood there was the xiang; for the larger districts there was the xu; and in the capitals there was the college. Every year some entered the college, and every second year there was a comparative examination. In the first year it was seen whether they could read the texts intelligently, and what was the meaning of each; in the third year, whether they were reverently attentive to their work, and what companionship was most pleasant to them; in the fifth year, how they extended their studies and sought the company of their teachers; in the seventh year, how they could discuss the subjects of their studies and select their friends. They were now said to have made some small attainments. In the ninth year, when they knew the different classes of subjects and had gained a general intelligence, were firmly established and would not fall back, they were said to have made grand attainments. After this the training was sufficient to transform the people, and to change (anything bad in) manners and customs. Those who lived near at hand submitted with delight, and those who were far off thought (of the teaching) with longing desire. Such was the method of the Great learning 古之教者，家有塾，黨有庠，術有序，國有學。比年入學，中年考校。一年視離經辨志，三年視敬業樂群，五年視博習親師，七年視論學取友，謂之小成；九年知類通達，強立而不反，謂之大成。夫然後足以化民易俗，近者說服，而遠者懷之，此大學之道也。(translated by James Legge)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: no

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The "Wangzhi" chapter narrated different ancient rulers' institutions of taking care for elderly and infirm. The "Yueling" chapter also specify that the aged and decaying received special care in the second month of autumn (zhongqiu zhi yue 仲秋之月).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The education recorded in the Liji was basically moral learning that aimed for pacifying the society and maintaining the social hierarchy.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The "Liyun" 禮運 chapter argued that to ensure every needed person, including aged (lao 老), widows (jingua 矜寡), orphans (gudu 孤獨), and disabled men (feiji 廢疾) could be sufficiently fed, virtuous and wise men were appointed in the ancient times. The "Yueling" chapter further prescribed the rulers to open the granaries to assist the impoverished and friendless in the last month of spring (jichun zhi yue 季春之月).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The Liji presented an ideal educational system which was assumed to be practiced in antiquity. However, the educational system in imperial China was different from what the Liji recorded.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: As a text for the imperial examinations, the Liji itself was studied and annotated in every generation that we can name several commentaries on this anthology. The following are three examples: Liji zhengyi 禮記正義, commented and annotated by Zheng Xuan 鄭玄 and Kong Yingda 孔穎達 Daxue

zhangju 大學章句 and Zhongyong zhangju 中庸章句, annotated by Zhu Xi Liji jijie 禮記集解, annotated by Sun Xidan 孫希旦. *The Liji has also been studied in Korea and Japan.

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Reference: Hua 華, Zhe 喆. Li Shi Zhengxue: Han Tang Jian Jingdian Quanshi Bianqian Shigao 禮是鄭學: 漢唐間經典詮釋變遷史論稿. Sheng huo-Du shu-Xin zhi san lian shu dian, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

— Yes

Notes: The "Tan gong shang" 檀弓上 regulated that students must treat their teachers in the way as if treating the parents, "In serving his father, (a son) should conceal (his faults), and not openly or strongly remonstrate with him about them; should in every possible way wait on and nourish him, without being tied to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and then complete the mourning for him for three' years. In serving his ruler, (a minister), should remonstrate with him openly and strongly (about his faults), and make no concealment (of them); should in every possible way wait on and nourish him, but according to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and should then wear mourning for him according to rule for three years. In serving his master, (a learner) should have nothing to do with openly reproving him or with concealing (his faults); should in every possible way wait upon and serve him, without being tied to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and mourn for him in heart for three years" 事親有隱而無犯，左右就養無方，服勤至死，致喪三年。事君有犯而無隱，左右就養有方，服勤至死，方喪三年。事師無犯無隱，左右就養無方，服勤至死，心喪三年。(James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

— Yes

Notes: The moral education the Liji advocated would lead to social stability and utopia--Great Unity (datong 大同)--in which people live at peace and everyone would get what they need.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: We cannot determine who were the producers of the chapters in the Liji. However, given that the Liji described in detail the ritual process and institution of government, it is reasonable to assume that the scholar-officials in the past participated in the production of the text. In the meantime, the emperors also had the right to decide the orthodox versions of the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Literati or scholar-officials; emperors

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: no

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yue Ling" 月令 chapter discusses how the misuse of seasonal proceedings would lead to famine. It therefore urges that governmental proceedings should be put into practice in accordance with the proper seasons to avoid such a disaster.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

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now said to have made some small attainments. In the ninth year, when they knew the different classes of subjects and had gained a general intelligence, were firmly established and would not fall back, they were said to have made grand attainments. After this the training was sufficient to transform the people, and to change (anything bad in) manners and customs. Those who lived near at hand submitted with delight, and those who were far off thought (of the teaching) with longing desire. Such was the method of the Great learning 古之教者，家有塾，黨有庠，術有序，國有學。比年入學，中年考校。一年視離經辨志，三年視敬業樂群，五年視博習親師，七年視論學取友，謂之小成；九年知類通達，強立而不反，謂之大成。夫然後足以化民易俗，近者說服，而遠者懷之，此大學之道也。(translated by James Legge)

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Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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達 Daxue zhangju 大學章句 and Zhongyong zhangju 中庸章句, annotated by Zhu Xi Liji jijie 禮記集解, annotated by Sun Xidan 孫希旦. *The Liji has also been studied in Korea and Japan.

Reference: 工藤卓司, Takushi Kudō. "Jin Bainian Lai Riben Xuezhe Sanli Zhi Yanjiu 近百年來日本學者《三禮》之研究", n.d..

Reference: Hua 華, Zhe 喆. Li Shi Zhengxue: Han Tang Jian Jingdian Quanshi Bianqian Shigao 禮是鄭學: 漢唐間經典詮釋變遷史論稿. Sheng huo·Du shu·Xin zhi san lian shu dian, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Tan gong shang" 檀弓上 regulated that students must treat their teachers in the way as if treating the parents, "In serving his father, (a son) should conceal (his faults), and not openly or strongly remonstrate with him about them; should in every possible way wait on and nourish him, without being tied to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and then complete the mourning for him for three years. In serving his ruler, (a minister), should remonstrate with him openly and strongly (about his faults), and make no concealment (of them); should in every possible way wait on and nourish him, but according to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and should then wear mourning for him according to rule for three years. In serving his master, (a learner) should have nothing to do with openly reproving him or with concealing (his faults); should in every possible way wait upon and serve him, without being tied to definite rules; should serve him laboriously till his death, and mourn for him in heart for three years" 事親有隱而無犯，左右就養無方，服勤至死，致喪三年。事君有犯而無隱，左右就養有方，服勤至死，方喪三年。事師無犯無隱，左右就養無方，服勤至死，心喪三年. (James Legge's translation)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: The moral education the Liji advocated would lead to social stability and utopia--Great Unity (datong 大同)--in which people live at peace and everyone would get what they need.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Wangzhi" chapter of the Liji presented a detailed and structural bureaucratic system that was supposed to be practiced in the ancient times. The system regulated the duties, lands, salaries, and so on, of the rulers and other officials in accordance with their rankings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" chapter regulated what officials were allowed or not allowed to do in different seasons or months.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Notes: The "Wangzhi" chapter mentioned the existence of public fields (gongtian 公田) in the ideal antiquity. Farmers were required to farm on the public fields. However, no tax was imposed on the public fields.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The institutionalized troops could only be sent to conquer and punish the unrighteous, accordingly to the "Yueling" chapter's description, "The son of Heaven also orders the leaders and commanders to choose men and sharpen weapons, to select and exercise those of distinguished merit, and to give their entire trust only to men whose services have been proved - thereby to correct all unrighteousness. (He instructs them also) to make enquiries about and punish the oppressive and insolent - thereby making it clear whom he loves and whom he hates, and giving effect to (the wishes of) the people, even the most distant from court" 天子乃命將帥，選士厲兵，簡練桀俊，專任有功，以征不義。詰誅暴慢，以明好惡，順彼遠方。 (James Legge's translation) Moreover, the troops were strictly trained and managed according to rituals. In the "Qu li shang" 曲禮上, it was said that "The majesty and dignity cannot be shown in assigning the different places at court, in the government of the armies, and in discharging the duties of office so as to secure the operation of the laws" 班朝治軍，蒞官行法，非禮威嚴

不行 (James Legge's translation, slightly modified)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yueling" chapter regulated the months of a year (e.g., the first month of spring 孟春之月) in which warfare was not allowed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Fishing

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Fishing

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 551 BCE - 220 CE

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